

LRMS and HRMS-based metabolite profiling of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* produced under variable salinity

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Abstract

This study evaluated the phytochemical profile of *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, a freshwater microalga that can also be produced using seawater, with particular attention to phenolic compounds and pigments. To the best of the authors knowledge, this is the first study providing a comparative and molecular-level characterisation of the phenolic composition of *S. almeriensis* under freshwater and seawater production conditions. After optimising the ultrasound-assisted extraction process (using a methanol-water mixture at a ratio of 80:20 v/v for 10 min), a UHPLC-QqQ method was validated for quantifying molecules such as trans-ferulic acid ($104 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), syringic acid ($27 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), catechin ($12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and sinapic acid ($12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Untargeted analysis using HRMS (Q-Orbitrap), multivariate modelling (PCA, OPLS-DA, VIP > 1.5) and univariate analysis led to the tentative identification of 58 compounds, of which seven were confirmed as metabolites using reference standards. This approach goes beyond conventional colorimetric methods commonly applied in previous studies on *Scenedesmus*, allowing a detailed molecular profiling of phenolic constituents. Production using seawater promoted the selective accumulation of antioxidant compounds and pigments without significantly affecting biomass productivity or photosynthetic efficiency, highlighting seawater acclimatisation as a viable strategy to modulate the phytochemical composition of freshwater microalgae for biotechnological applications.

Keywords: Bioactive compounds, secondary metabolites, targeted analysis, untargeted analysis, LRMS, HRMS

1. Introduction

By 2050, the world's population is expected to reach 10 billion people. This population growth, combined with ongoing industrialisation, is putting considerable pressure on food production systems and agricultural resources. Indeed, estimations suggest that demand for food could increase by up to 56% [1]. In this context, it is necessary to identify renewable and sustainable sources that offer both economic and environmental benefits.

Microalgae are emerging as a promising alternative for enhancing food security and improve environmental quality [2]. They can be used as food directly, mainly as food colourants or as a source of high-quality protein [3]. They can also be used to produce food indirectly, either as animal feed ingredients or as agricultural products, such as biostimulants and biofertilisers. These organisms can enhance crop growth and development, improve nutrient use efficiency, and reduce dependence on conventional chemical inputs. Consequently, they promote greener agricultural practices and contribute to food security by producing healthier, more nutritious food [4]. One of the main advantages of microalgae is their rapid growth rate and their ability to be produced using different types of water (e.g., wastewater or seawater). These microorganisms are known for their rich content of bioactive molecules, such as pigments, proteins, fatty acids, polysaccharides, vitamins, and phenolic compounds, all of which are of great interest in the preparation of a wide range of products, including food, cosmetics and nutraceuticals [2,5,6].

Recent studies have shown that the concentration of phenolic compounds varies significantly among different microalgae species including *Scenedesmus* sp., *Dunaliella salina*, *Chlorella minutissima* and *Nannochloropsis oculata*. In these

microalgae, several classes of flavonoids, including flavanols, flavanones, isoflavones and dihydrochalcones have been identified [7,8]. These phenolic compounds play a multifunctional role in microalgal physiology, acting as key mediators in the response to environmental stresses such as oxidative, saline and light stress. They contribute to the neutralisation of reactive oxygen species, provide protection against radiation, and participate in cellular signalling pathways and defence mechanisms against pathogens. Among them, flavonoids are of particular interest due to their wide range of bioactivities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and cytotoxic effects, which explains their growing relevance for applications in the cosmetic, food and pharmaceutical industries [8,9]. Other studies have confirmed the presence of specific phenolic acids such as ferulic, p-coumaric and gallic acids in *Scenedesmus* strains [8]. However, to date, most research has primarily focused on the quantification of total phenolic and flavonoid contents using conventional colorimetric methods, particularly the Folin–Ciocalteu assay. For example, Öktem et al. (2019) studied a thermotolerant strain of *Scenedesmus sp.* and measured a total phenolic content of $5.40 \pm 0.28 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in ethanol/water extracts. Despite being useful information, there is a need to move towards protocols that allow selective extraction and molecular profiling of these compounds to maximise their biotechnological exploitation [7,10].

The biosynthesis of phenolic compounds in microalgae is heavily influenced by abiotic stimuli such as ultraviolet radiation, temperature fluctuations and light intensity, which is reflected in these organisms' ability to adapt to changing environmental conditions [8]. The microalga *S. almeriensis* is a freshwater species that has recently been adapted to seawater [11]. Producing this

microalga in seawater led to changes in its bioactive properties [11]. There are studies on phenolic profiles in different microalgal species and specific studies on the extraction and quantification of phenols in species of the genus *Scenedesmus*. However, there is a lack of specific comparative evaluation of the total phenol content in *S. almeriensis* after controlled acclimatisation to seawater. Furthermore, although previous studies indicated that saline stress could modify phenol synthesis in microalgae, the effect of salinity on the phenolic composition of freshwater strains remains poorly characterised [12]. For this reason, this study aimed to evaluate the phytochemical profile of *S. almeriensis* by quantifying total phenolic compounds and characterising metabolites using low resolution mass spectrometry (LRMS) and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) with a triple quadrupole (QqQ) and a Q-Orbitrap mass analyser, respectively. In addition, the study assessed whether the use of seawater during the biomass production stage affected the production and accumulation of these compounds.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

The reagents and solvents used were of analytical and HPLC grade, respectively. Ultrapure water was obtained from a Milli-Q system (Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) and methanol and ethanol were purchased from Honeywell (Morristown, NJ, USA). Formic acid (>99% purity) was obtained from Fisher Scientific (Pittsburgh, PA, USA). Florisil® from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, Missouri, USA) was used for sample clean-up. BD Discardit™ II 2- and 5-mL syringes (Huesca, Spain) and Captiva nylon syringe filters with a pore size of 0.20 µm

(Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) were used for extract filtration. Analytical standards with a purity of >95% were acquired for optimising the method. Ferulic acid, catechin, caffeic acid, naringenin, quercetin and syringic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). Rutin, sinapic acid, luteolin (purity 92.92%) and kaempferol were obtained from Dr Ehrenstorfer™ (Augsburg, Germany). Some of the compounds were obtained during the confirmation step of the untargeted analysis. These included 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and coumarin (purity >99%) from Sigma-Aldrich, carvacrol, cinnamic acid and thymol (purity >98%) from Tokyo Chemical Industry (Tokyo, Japan), and lutein and zeaxanthin (purity >80%) from Dr. Ehrenstorfer™.

All standards were stored in a freezer at -18 °C until use. Individual stock solutions were prepared at a concentration of 0.5 g·L⁻¹ by dissolving 5 mg in 10 mL of methanol. These solutions were stored in amber glass vials at -18 °C. Intermediate solutions were prepared in methanol containing all the compounds of interest at a final concentration of 0.005 g·L⁻¹. These solutions were also stored in amber glass vials under the same conditions.

2.2. Microalgae used and production conditions

The strain used for this study was *Scenedesmus almeriensis* (CCAP 276/24) available at CIESOL Solar Energy Research Centre (Almeria, Spain). The culture medium was prepared using commercial fertilisers and consisted of 0.90 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄ and 0.03 g·L⁻¹ Karentol® (Konegard, Barcelona, Spain). The latter is a micronutrient solution that provides essential trace elements such as B, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, and Zn. The medium was

prepared using either distilled water or seawater. The cells produced using seawater underwent a progressive adaptation process, gradually increasing the proportion of seawater in the culture medium from 0 to 100%, equivalent to an NaCl concentration range of 0 to 515 mM (data not shown).

Biomass production was carried out using 300 mL-controlled bubble columns with a working volume of 250 mL as described in a previous study [13]. Three independent photobioreactors were used per treatment, each one representing an experimental unit. Light was provided using 28 W fluorescent lamps (Philips Daylight T5, Madrid, Spain), arranged horizontally with a separation of 1 cm between tubes and located approximately 4 cm from the surface of the production system. The irradiance inside the columns, in the absence of biomass, was $1,850 \mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, measured with an SQS-100 spherical quantum sensor (Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany). The light regime was programmed to simulate outdoor conditions, establishing a photoperiod of light:dark 12:12 h, with a progressive increase in light intensity from 08:00 to 14:00, followed by a gradual decrease between 14:00 and 20:00. The temperature and pH were controlled at 25 °C and 8.0, respectively.

The reactors were initially operated in batch mode for 22 days. Subsequently, the reactors were operated in semi-continuous mode, with a dilution rate of 0.3 day^{-1} , equivalent to a daily renewal of 30% of the culture with fresh medium. The semi-continuous production phase lasted approximately 18 days, meaning that the total volume of the photobioreactors was replaced 9 times. Harvesting was performed by centrifugation using a Digicen 22 centrifuge (Ortoalresa, Madrid, Spain) operating at $5,000 \times g$ for 10 min. The biomass was washed once with distilled water, lyophilised, and stored at -20 °C until further use. The results

presented in this study are the average of three consecutive sampling days during the steady-state phase. Each sampling day was a technical replicate and each photobioreactor a natural replicate.

2.2.1 Determination of the performance of the culture

Biomass concentration was quantified using the dry weight method. Twenty millilitres of the culture were filtered through a 0.2 μm filter, and the residue was dried in an oven at 80 °C for 24 h. To determine the chlorophyll fluorescence ratio (Fv/Fm), the samples were left in the dark for 15 min, and their fluorescence was measured using an AquaPen AP 100 (Photon System Instruments, Czech Republic). Additionally, the absorbance of the culture was recorded daily within the 400–780 nm range using a GENESYS 10S UV–Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Spain). All these analytical determinations were carried out in triplicate per natural replicate.

2.3. Ultrasound probe-assisted extraction

To extract the phenolic compounds, 250 mg of lyophilised microalgal biomass were weighed and mixed with 5 mL of a methanol:water solution (4:1, v/v). The mixture was sonicated using a SONOPLUS HD4200 sonicator from Bandelin Electronic GmbH (Berlin, Germany) for 10 min at 20 kHz and 200 W. Temperature was kept below 40 °C by immersing the sample in an ice bath. After sonication, the sample was centrifuged for 20 min at 5,000 x g (Universal 320R centrifuge from Hettich Zentrifugen (Tuttlingen, Germany)). From the resulting supernatant, 1.5 mL were taken for the clean-up phase, to which 100 mg of Florisil[®] were added for dispersive solid-phase extraction (dSPE), employing a multitube vortex

from Benchmark Scientific (Sayreville, NJ, USA). After a second centrifugation step at 5,000 x g for 10 min, the supernatant was collected with a 2 mL syringe and passed through a 0.2 µm nylon filter. Finally, 1 mL of the clarified extract was transferred to a glass vial for subsequent chromatographic analysis. Three extractions were done per natural replicate.

2.4. Total Phenolic Content Quantification

To determine the total phenol content, the Folin–Ciocalteu method was used. The method applied was based on the study of Ainsworth and Gillespie [14]. First, 200 µL of the microalgae extract were pipetted into a test tube, to which 950 µL of distilled water and 50 µL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent were then added. After incubation of the mixture for 3 min at room temperature, 1.5 mL of a 7% sodium carbonate solution and 800 µL of distilled water were added. The mixture was left to stand in the dark for 30 min, and then the absorbance at 765 nm was measured using a UV-vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The total phenol content was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per gram of dry microalgae extract ($\text{mg GAE} \times \text{g MA}^{-1}$). All technical replicates were conducted in triplicate, and the results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation.

2.5. Chromatographic analysis

After extraction both targeted and untargeted analyses were performed. Targeted analyses were performed using a 1290 Infinity I Series liquid chromatograph from Agilent Technologies, coupled to a 6460 triple quadrupole, also from Agilent

Technologies, and equipped with an electrospray ionisation (ESI) source. Analysis was performed in both positive and negative modes using nitrogen as the collision gas. The ionisation source conditions were as follows: curtain gas temperature 300 °C, drying gas temperature 350 °C, drying gas flow rate 5 L·min⁻¹, nebuliser pressure 45 psi, curtain gas flow rate 11 L·min⁻¹, and capillary voltage 3500 V (ESI+), 3500 V (ESI-). Data analysis was performed using MassHunter Quantitative Analysis 10.0 software.

For the untargeted analysis, a Vanquish Flex Quaternary LC Thermo Fisher Scientific equipped with a quaternary pump, a degasser, an autosampler (with a 100 µL injection loop) and a hybrid Q-Exactive Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Q-Exactive), operating in both positive and negative ionization modes, was employed. The MS parameters were as follows: spray voltage, 4 kV; sheath gas (N₂, 95%), 35 (arbitrary units (au)); auxiliary gas (N₂, 95%), 10 (au); S-lens RF level, 50 (au); heater temperature, 305 °C; and capillary temperature, 300 °C. Mass spectra were acquired using full MS and data-independent acquisition (DIA-MS/MS) in ESI+ and ESI-. Full MS was performed with a mass resolving power set at 70,000 full width at half maximum (FWHM) at *m/z* 200, AGC target at 10⁶; and a mass range between *m/z* 100 and 1500. DIA was performed using higher collisional dissociation (HCD) with a collision energy of 30 eV. The mass resolution was 35,000 FWHM at *m/z* 200, AGC target 2 × 10⁵, and the isolation window *m/z* 50.

To ensure quality results, samples were injected by quintuplicate, including extraction and system blanks. They were injected randomly across worklist. Triphenyl phosphate was employed as internal standard for signal normalization. Data processing was performed using Xcalibur™ version 4.3.73 software, Quan

and Qual Browsers, and TraceFinder 5.1 platform (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Les Ulis, France). Theoretical prediction of the fragmentation of suspected compounds was performed using MassFrontier™ v7.0 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Compound Discoverer™ v3.2 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was employed for annotation of untargeted bioactive compounds, and SIMCA v17.0.2 (Sartorius) and Microsoft excel for statistical analysis to compare freshwater and seawater cultures.

For both methodologies chromatographic separation was performed using a Hypersil Gold aQ column (100x2.1 mm, 1.9 µm particle size) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (San Jose, CA, USA). The column was maintained at 40 °C. The mobile phases used were water 0.1% formic acid and methanol at a flow rate of 0.3 mL·min⁻¹. The elution gradient started at 95% of the aqueous phase and was kept constant for 1 min. The percentage was reduced to 70% in 3 min and to 0% in 4 min. This percentage was maintained for 2 min, followed by a return to initial conditions after 0.5 min and stabilization for 4.5 min. The total run time was 15 min, and the injection volume was 10 µL.

2.6. Statistical analysis

To reduce the number of entities during untargeted analysis and evaluate the differences between *S. almeriensis* samples grown in freshwater and seawater, a multivariate statistical analysis was performed. For this, SIMCA v17.0.2 (Sartorius) software was used, and different statistical analyses were performed: Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied as an exploratory multivariate tool to provide an overview of global metabolite differences between freshwater-

and seawater-grown *S. almeriensis* ($R^2 > 0.5$ with a p -value < 0.05). Orthogonal partial least squares-discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA), ($Q^2 > 0.5$, to ensure a good fit of the model to the data) and variable importance in projection (VIP) values (>1.5) to distinguish the compounds that differentiated the cultures. VIP-based prioritisation was complemented by univariate statistical testing with false discovery rate (FDR) correction. Specifically, Mann–Whitney U tests adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini–Hochberg FDR were performed to confirm significant differences between culture media for VIP compounds.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Biomass production

The comparison between freshwater and seawater production was first evaluated in terms of overall physiological performance and biomass production. These parameters determined the feasibility of saline production strategies from a biomass perspective. Despite exposure to seawater conditions, *S. almeriensis* maintained a stable physiological functionality, as reflected by the Fv/Fm values ranging from 0.60 to 0.65 throughout the production period (**Figure 1A**). These values are within the range commonly associated with healthy non-stressed microalgal cultures, according to Morillas España 2020, indicating that photosystem II efficiency and cellular integrity were not severely compromised by salinity [15]. It is important to highlight that the strain was adapted to seawater after an adaptive evolution process (data not shown).

According to biomass productivity data, **Figure 1B** shows the effect of seawater on the growth of the microalga *S. almeriensis*. The microalga produced in

freshwater reached a biomass concentration of around $2.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, compared to $1.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ obtained when using seawater ($p < 0.05$). When the semi-continuous regime was implemented between days 22 and 40, the biomass concentration remained relatively stable at between 1.7 and $2.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for several days, indicating that the system has achieved a steady state. In seawater production, however, the observed values were lower, ranging from 1.2 to $1.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Such behaviour is characteristic of semi-continuous cultures, in which the medium is partially extracted and replaced to allow the microalgae to remain in an active growth phase. Although seawater production resulted in a moderate reduction in biomass productivity compared to freshwater, the maintenance of photosynthetic efficiency suggested that the strain effectively acclimated to saline conditions rather than experiencing acute stress. This physiological resilience is particularly relevant in the context of seawater-based production, as it indicates that reduced freshwater availability does not necessarily translate into impaired cellular performance or metabolic collapse. These results are particularly interesting considering that freshwater consumption was reduced by up to 90 % and this strategy minimised the proliferation of pathogens and parasites in large-scale cultures [11,16]. The reduction does not reach 100% because the water lost through evaporation during production cannot be fully compensated for with seawater, as this would lead to a progressive accumulation of salts in the medium. This would increase osmotic stress and negatively affect the growth of microalgae [17]. Consequently, partial replacement with fresh water is necessary to maintain salinity within physiologically acceptable ranges.

Comparing these results with previous ones, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies evaluating the effect of salt stress on biomass production for *S.*

almeriensis. Various studies have shown that the response of other algae such as *C. vulgaris* to salt stress depends on the salt concentration and manifests itself rapidly in the initial stages of production. At high concentrations, microalgae underwent cell death and a notable reduction in cell size was observed due to the osmotic imbalance experienced at the start of production [18]. Conversely, when a higher salinity was used, *C. vulgaris* was able to grow and generate biomass at levels that were only slightly lower than those obtained with pure freshwater, and it also showed a greater accumulation of lipids. However, this benefit was accompanied by a slower growth rate, which was attributable to the osmotic stress that intermediate salinity continued to impose [19]. Finally, increasing salinity further up to 80‰ clearly inhibited the growth of *Chlorella* strains, confirming that there is a critical threshold of salt tolerance beyond which the proliferation of microalgae is prevented [20]. In the production of *Arthrospira platensis* using seawater, a decrease in biomass concentration was observed compared to production in freshwater, with values of 0.90 g·L⁻¹ and 0.98 g·L⁻¹, respectively. Likewise, the culture developed in seawater presented a longer adaptation phase. When the semi-continuous production phase was implemented, the difference between the two treatments became more pronounced, with a reduction in biomass from 22.9 g·m⁻²·día⁻¹ in freshwater to 16.3 g·m⁻²·día⁻¹ in seawater [12]. In conclusion, the biomass productivity achieved in this study was comparable to that obtained in previous studies using other algae species.

[15][16]3.2. Mass spectrometric optimisation

To perform a targeted analysis and evaluate the extraction efficiency, the spectrometric conditions were first optimised for the targeted compounds.

Compounds were selected according to previous reports describing phenolic acids and flavonoids commonly detected in microalgae and the availability of analytical reference standards [21,22]. While the targeted list does not aim to be exhaustive, it was conceived to cover structurally diverse and biologically relevant phenolic classes that could reasonably be expected in *S. almeriensis* based on the existing literature. Individually prepared solutions of the target standards at a concentration of 0.01 g·L⁻¹ in methanol:water (50:50, v/v) were injected into the QqQ mass spectrometer. The ESI+ ionisation mode was used for kaempferol, while ESI- was selected for the remaining compounds. The ionisation energies were optimised using the full scan mode (energies evaluated ranged from 75 to 200 V) and the collision energies were optimised with the “product ion” mode, in which quadrupole 2 acts as a collision cell (energies evaluated ranged from 5 to 50 eV). The ions were selected according to their highest signals without interferences. The MS/MS parameters for each studied compound studied are shown in supporting information (**Table S1**).

3.3. Extraction optimisation

To evaluate the appropriate methodology for determining the composition of *S. almeriensis* grown in both freshwater and seawater, several parameters were evaluated. Three extraction methods were used. In all the methods, 250 mg of freeze-dried biomass and 5 mL of methanol:water 80:20 (v/v) or ethanol:water 50:50 (v/v) were used, except for those tests where a different volume was specified:

- Extraction 1. Ultrasonic bath employing extraction times of 15 min, triple extraction (15 min each; 2 mL per extraction) and 60 min, at 0 °C (ice bath) and 50 °C.
- Extraction 2. Rotatory agitator for 30 min, 1 h, triple extraction (1 h each; 2 mL per extraction) and 4 h at room temperature (25 °C).
- Extraction 3. Ultrasonic probe and extraction times of 5, 10 and 15 min in an ice bath.

After solvent extraction, all samples were centrifuged for 20 min to separate the solids and recover the supernatant. From this, 1.5 mL was collected and 100 mg of Florisil® was added as a pretreatment to remove excess chlorophyll and reduce equipment contamination without affecting the recovery of the compounds of interest [23]. After vortexing the mixture for 30 s and centrifuging again for 10 min, 1 mL of the purified supernatant was collected. This procedure was performed in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the method and the analytical quality of the results.

To compare each extraction condition, the final extracts were analysed using the Folin–Ciocalteu method [14]. Although this method is not completely selective for phenolic compounds [14], it provides an estimate and a broad overview for the selection of the most appropriate extraction method. In general, results showed that the higher the extraction time, the higher the phenolic compound yields (**Figure 2**). Additionally, the methanol:water mixture (80:20, v/v) allowed better performance than the ethanol:water mixture (50:50, v/v) for all tested conditions.

The lowest concentrations were reached when an ultrasound bath was used, ranging from 1.49 to 1.85 mg of GAE·g⁻¹ of MA for 15 min of extraction, from 1.68

to 1.99 mg of GAE·g⁻¹ of MA for 60 min of extraction, and from 2.00 to 2.12 mg of GAE·g⁻¹ of MA for triple extraction during 15 min each (even knowing that a higher sample dilution was produced). Although the concentrations were slightly lower when the extraction temperature was set at 50 °C, no significant differences were found between 0 and 50 °C. When a rotatory agitator was used, the concentrations increased, although it should be noted that extraction times were generally higher (between 30 and 240 min). The highest concentrations were obtained for 240 min of extraction and for the triple extraction of 60 min each (180 min in total). Concentrations ranged between 2.08 and 3.21 g·mg GAE⁻¹ MA. Finally, due to the high extraction energy of the probe ultrasound, this method provided the highest yields, despite extraction times being the lowest. The concentrations slightly improved between 5 min of extraction (4.08-4.81 g·mg GAE·g⁻¹ MA) and 10 min (4.28-5.18 mg GAE·g⁻¹ of MA), while for 15 min they were very similar to 10 min (4.27-5.21 mg GAE·g⁻¹ of MA). Furthermore, longer extraction times made it difficult to maintain the samples at low temperature, so 10 min was the selected extraction time, minimising the probability of compound degradation caused by heat.

The selected method has previously been identified as the most suitable by Duan et al. for other microalgae, confirming the results obtained in this work [24]. A previous study by Keddar et al. on *Scenedesmus sp.* showed similar concentrations using an extraction with supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS) (8.60 ± 0.90 mg GAE·g⁻¹ DW) [25], highlighting the suitability of the method developed. In fact, other studies using solid-liquid extraction with a mixture of ethanol:water (0.50-4.60 mg GAE·g⁻¹ biomass) or methanol:water (0.70-3.50 mg GAE·g⁻¹ DW) obtained concentrations lower than those of the proposed method, which means

that probe ultrasound has a higher extraction efficiency, at least when the Folin–Ciocalteu method was applied [26,27]. Although probe-assisted ultrasound extraction was applied at laboratory scale in this study, comparable cell disruption efficiencies are expected to be achieved at industrial scale using high-power, continuous-flow ultrasonic systems or high-pressure homogenisers, which are being used at the commercial level.

The final QqQ method was validated to ensure its suitability for the bioactive compounds present in *Scenedesmus* strains. Several parameters were evaluated: linearity, matrix effect, trueness, precision, and the estimation of the limits of quantification (LOQs). Complete validation is included in the supporting information (**Table S2**). Briefly, all compounds showed good R^2 values in the range of 1–120 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, matrix effects ranging from 0.52 to 1.07, recoveries from 70.80 to 119.50%, and precision values in terms of RSDs lower than or equal to 24.50%. The LOQ was established at 10 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ for all compounds. The values obtained confirm that the proposed methodology is adequate for the analysis of bioactive compounds.

3.4. Targeted and untargeted analysis

From a biomass quality perspective, the comparison between freshwater and seawater production aims to determine whether salinity-induced metabolic changes translate into functionally relevant modifications of the biomass, rather than merely compositional differences. The targeted compounds were measured in *S. almeriensis* lyophilised biomass cultured in freshwater following the proposed methodology (section 2.4). The results showed that all compounds

were detected in the samples, although only four of them were identified above the LOQ (**Table 1**). The highest concentration was found for trans-ferulic acid ($104 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), followed by syringic acid ($27 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), catechin ($12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and sinapic acid ($12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Direct comparison between freshwater and seawater production revealed a selective modulation of the phenolic compound profile: seawater production resulted in slightly higher concentrations of several phenolic acids, including trans-ferulic, sinapic and syringic acids.

Several studies have demonstrated the phytochemical richness of microalgae in terms of their content of phenolic compounds and flavonoids. For example, a study analysing various species found ferulic acid derivatives at concentrations between 0.63 and $2.01 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ [21]. Similarly, Gaurav et al. [28] detected phenols derived from the same acid at significantly higher levels of $17.60 \pm 0.85 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, suggesting variations dependent on strain and culture conditions. In contrast, another study of different microalgae identified catechin and syringic acid with detection limits (LOD) of 0.13 and $0.03 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and LOQs of 0.44 and $0.09 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively [29]. Direct quantitative comparison with previously reported phenolic concentrations should be interpreted with caution, as most available data correspond to different species or strains and were obtained under distinct production, extraction and analytical conditions. In particular, variations in solvent systems, extraction energy and the use of colorimetric versus LC-MS-based approaches are known to strongly influence the reported phenolic content in microalgae [21]. Therefore, the literature values are provided to contextualize the range of phenolic concentrations reported for microalgae rather than as a strict benchmark.

In addition to the targeted compounds, an untargeted approach was followed using a Q-Orbitrap analyser to identify as many compounds as possible. Data obtained from sample analysis with the HRMS system were directly uploaded to Compound Discoverer 3.2 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific), which integrates multiple databases for the preliminary identification of compounds. The Phenol-Explorer platform was also used to generate an initial list of phenolic compounds from the raw data obtained by HRMS. This list contained around 332 putative identified compounds. Some restrictions were then applied to reduce the number of false positives: good peak shapes, an intensity threshold of 10^4 , logical retention times (after 1 min and before 13 min), exclusion of compounds with halogen in their structure, and logical isotopic patterns with respect to their theoretical molecular formula. Finally, compounds already detected using the targeted approach were also eliminated. Applying these parameters, 127 compounds were left. These compounds were identified with confidence between levels 4 and 5 (only molecular formulas based on their exact mass and a few characteristics, such as isotopic patterns, are known [30]).

PCA was applied to reduce the complexity of the dataset, allowing visualization of similarities and differences between samples based on their overall metabolite composition. The PCA score plot shows a clear separation between freshwater and seawater and the extraction solvent (methanol and water at a ratio of 80:20 versus ethanol and water at a ratio of 50:50, v/v), indicating that salinity is a major factor influencing the metabolic profile. Importantly, PCA does not identify individual compounds per se, but highlights coordinated changes across groups of metabolites, thereby supporting the conclusion that seawater production induces a systematic and selective metabolic adjustment. Next, multivariate

statistical analysis (**Figure 3**) was employed to examine the differences between the culture conditions in more detail. The PCA analysis demonstrated significant descriptive power ($R^2 = 0.83$ with three principal components; $p < 0.05$), regardless of the solvent employed; however, the final extraction was conducted using a methanol:water mixture (80:20, v/v). Due to the small sample size ($n = 5$ for each treatment/extraction group), these results should be considered preliminary.

The OPLS-DA model reinforced the discrimination between groups, reaching a Q^2 value of 0.96 and indicating excellent predictive power. Given the limited sample size, model robustness was evaluated by permutation testing (200 permutations), which resulted in a negative Q^2 intercept, indicating that the observed class separation was not driven by random chance (**Figure S1**). Nevertheless, OPLS-DA results were interpreted cautiously and used to complement unsupervised PCA and compound-specific quantitative analyses. VIP value analysis identified the compounds that contributed most to separating the samples. **Figure S2** shows the proportion of metabolites with $VIP > 1.5$ for the methanol:water 80:20 (v/v) extraction. Univariate analysis followed by FDR correction identified 22 features showing statistically significant differences between freshwater and seawater production (FDR-adjusted $p \leq 0.05$). These features largely overlapped with compounds contributing to the multivariate separation identified by OPLS-DA (**Table S3**). Among these, key phenolic acids and derivatives (e.g. cinnamic, benzoic and 4-hydroxybenzoic acids), lignan-related compounds (syringaresinol and lariciresinol), and stress-associated pigments such as xanthophylls (neoxanthin/prasinolaxanthin/violaxanthin) showed

consistent and statistically supported differences between freshwater and seawater production.

In summary, a clear distinction between freshwater and seawater production emerges when combining quantitative data (**Table 1**) with the untargeted HRMS profiling. Seawater production resulted in the up-regulation of a specific subset of phenolic-related compounds, as reflected by increased signal intensities (green bars in **Figure S2** for compounds with p-value < 0.05 in **Table S3**) and higher concentrations of untargeted compounds such as 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (54 to 72 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and cinnamic acid (11 to 21 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). In contrast, several phenolic derivatives exhibited higher relative abundance under freshwater conditions (yellow bars), including volatile and methoxylated phenols.

Against physiological background commented above, the observed biochemical differences between freshwater- and seawater-grown biomass can be interpreted as adaptive compositional adjustments rather than symptoms of cellular damage. At a global level, seawater production induced selective modifications in the metabolic profile of *S. almeriensis*, as evidenced by multivariate analysis and compound-specific quantification. The preferential increase of simple phenolic acids and phenylpropanoid-related metabolites under seawater conditions is consistent with stress-related metabolic adjustments [17], whereas most flavonoids included in the targeted analysis remained below the limit of quantification under both production regimes.

Analytical validation of the compounds (**Table S2**) confirmed the method's suitability, supporting the conclusion that the differences observed in PCA and

OPLS-DA are due to real variations in the chemical profile of the samples, rather than analytical interferences.

The putative compound list of potential compounds was reduced to 58 compounds, those with a VIP higher than 1.5. They were manually searched using the Xcalibur version 3.0 platform. The chromatographic time was compared with that in studies using a similar methodology as well as their fragmentation pattern, using the software MassFrontier™ v7.0 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) to estimate the fragmentation when it was not available in the literature. Taking into account these parameters, 12 compounds were assigned to a level of confidence 2 [30], since some fragments were found for each compound. In **Figure 4** and additional material (**Figures S3-S11**) show the identified compounds in *S. almeriensis* cultured in seawater: 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, cinnamic acid, coumarin, lutein, zeaxanthin, carvacrol, thymol, ellagic acid glucoside, lariciresinol, antheraxanthin, and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde.

To complement untargeted identification and increase the level of confidence, a confirmatory analysis was performed, in which each putative compound was compared to available reference standards and validated by exact mass matching (with a deviation of <5 ppm) and by checking its fragmentation pattern. This procedure confirmed the presence of key molecules with a high degree of structural certainty. Seven analytical standards were acquired, confirming 5 of them (level 1) as shown in **Figure 4** and **Figures S3-S6**: 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, cinnamic acid, coumarin, lutein, and carvacrol [30]. It should be noted that all these compounds were detected in both strains, the one produced using freshwater and the one produced using seawater. Some retention times varied slightly, probably because the standard analysis was performed several weeks

after the samples were analysed, as this was when the commercial suppliers were due to distribute them.

Carotenoids and xanthophylls, including antheraxanthin, were also detected, as well as a peak corresponding to lutein. These latter compounds had previously been described in microalgae of the genus *Scenedesmus* [31]. Specifically, **Figure 4** shows a chromatographic signal at a retention time of 12.63 min that generates three fragments simultaneously with m/z values of 338.26 and 476.36 (mass error of -1.23 and -1.18 ppm, respectively). The analysis of both standards individually confirmed that the detected compound was lutein, instead of zeaxanthin, which confirmed the presence of these xanthophylls in the biomass. From an applied perspective, the selective accumulation of antioxidant phenolic acids and high-value pigments under seawater conditions suggests a strategic trade-off, whereby reduced freshwater consumption and enhanced biomass functionality may offset moderate productivity losses.

The concentrations of the confirmed compounds were calculated with respect to the analytical standard signals. They are shown in **Table 1**. Their high abundance is consistent with the ability of *S. almeriensis* to bioaccumulate pigments in aquatic environments [32]. The simultaneous detection of phenolic acids and flavonoid glycosides aligns with the phytochemical profiles reported for *Scenedesmus obliquus* and other microalgal species [33]. As well as for targeted compounds, an increase was observed for the confirmed untargeted compounds when seawater was used, although it was more pronounced. Specifically, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (from 54 to 72 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), cinnamic acid (from 11 to 21 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), coumarin (from 1 to 2 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and lutein (from 293 to 409 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) increased their concentrations, while carvacrol (from 19 to 16 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) was reduced under

salinity conditions. Taken together, these results suggest that saline conditions induce selective changes in the production of secondary metabolites, favouring the accumulation of antioxidant compounds and nutraceutical pigments, even at the expense of moderate productivity losses. From a biomass production perspective, these results indicate that seawater production represents a trade-off between slightly reduced productivity and enhanced biochemical quality, which may be advantageous for integrated biorefinery approaches combining energy, nutraceutical and biomass-based applications.

This study focuses on a single freshwater microalgal strain adapted to seawater under controlled conditions. While the observed responses highlight the adaptive capacity of *S. almeriensis*, similar salinity-induced trends have been reported in other freshwater microalgae such as *A. platensis* or *C. vulgaris*, suggesting that selective metabolic modulation may represent a broader acclimation strategy rather than a strain-specific response [12,19].

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that *S. almeriensis* can be produced using seawater, at least at the laboratory scale. Despite a moderate decrease in biomass productivity, the cultures maintained physiological functionality and photosynthetic efficiency, indicating effective acclimation to saline conditions rather than severe stress.

Beyond productivity considerations, seawater production induced selective changes in biomass composition, favouring the accumulation of antioxidant-related metabolites and high-value pigments. Specifically, several phenolic acids

as well as flavonoids and xanthophylls (e.g. synapctic acid, ferulic acid or lutein) increased their concentrations under seawater conditions. These compositional shifts suggest that salinity can be strategically exploited to modulate biomass quality, enhancing its potential for applications beyond bulk bioenergy production, such as nutraceuticals, functional ingredients, or biorefinery-oriented processes.

Overall, the results highlight a trade-off between biomass yield and biochemical value, supporting the concept that seawater-based production may contribute to more sustainable and flexible microalgal production systems. By reducing competition for freshwater resources while enabling the production of functionally enriched biomass, seawater acclimatisation emerges as a promising approach for integrated biomass valorisation strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

E. Rivera-Sánchez: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Formal analysis and Writing – Original draft; **Jesus Marin-Sáez:** Conceptualisation, Writing – Review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation; **Antonia Garrido-Frenich:** Writing - Review & Editing, Resources; **T. Lafarga:** Writing - Review & editing, Supervision, and Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Table 1: Concentration values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) for the targeted and untargeted compounds in *Scenedesmus almeriensis*

Targeted compounds		
Compound	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	
	Freshwater	Seawater
Catechin	12	<10
Caffeic acid	<10	<10
Synaptic acid	27	30
Syringic acid	12	13
trans-Ferulic acid	104	112
Rutin	<10	<10
Quercetin	<10	<10
Naringenin	<10	<10
Kaempferol	<10	<10
Luteolin	<10	<10
Untargeted compounds		
Compound	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	
	Freshwater	Seawater
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	54	72
Cinnamic acid	11	21
Coumarin	1	2
Lutein	293	409
Carvacrol	19	16

Figure caption

Figure 1: (A) Variable fluorescence (F_v)/maximum fluorescence (F_m) value of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* culture in freshwater (green circles) and seawater (orange circles) for 42 days and (B) Biomass concentration. The values represent the average of three independent determinations. The vertical dashed line indicates the start of the semi-continuous production phase.

Figure 2: Total phenolic compound expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of dry microalgae extract ($\text{mg GAE}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ MA) using the Folin–Ciocalteu method. Extraction 1: Ultrasound bath; Extraction 2: Rotatory agitator; Extraction 3: Probe ultrasound. The dark colour shows the methanol:water (80:20, v/v) solvent and the light colour shows the ethanol:water (50:50, v/v) solvent

Figure 3: 2D and 3D PCA-X analysis comparing culture medium (freshwater and seawater) and extraction solvent (methanol:water (80:20, v/v) and ethanol: water (50:50, v/v))

Figure 4: Confirmation of lutein in *Scenedesmus* cultured in seawater with its analytical standard. A: lutein extracted ion chromatogram (EIC); B: EIC of lutein and zeaxanthin in the analytical standard ($250\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); C: Extracted fragment ion chromatogram of lutein; D: Experimental and theoretical mass spectrum of lutein